

STUDENT'S FACED COMPLICATION IN LANGUAGE LEARNING PROCESS

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Abstract: the aim of this paper is to describe some kind of problems that most students face while they are learning a new language and achievable solutions for them. It reveals some factors why students meet difficulties while studying and how they can overcome these challenges. Also this article recommends several websites and apps which can be appropriate for language learners.

Keywords: face, language, help, skill, English, problem, vocabulary, speaking, listen, watch, solutions..

1 INTRODUCTION

We have all learned a language, be it our mother tongue, a second language at school, or a more recent language for work or a holiday. It is so much a normal part of human behavior that we may not consciously think about the processes involved. Nevertheless, given that a second language is much less frequently learned to a high level of competence and the costs of failure are much greater, the interest in the way in which languages are learned is entirely appropriate and understandable. This is a topic of great importance to an educator or teacher too, as understanding how a language is acquired can greatly influence how they teach it. This also raises questions about the nature of the language that is learned. If it is possible (as many people claim) to get to a high level of competence in a second language, to the point where it can be used as a medium of instruction at university level, what exactly is the difference between a first and second language and what are the implications for second language teaching. This chapter deals with these questions with particular reference to the exploration of grammar by learners. This is in line with our major area of interest which is the development of written English. Many people would say that it is not possible to actually teach grammar and that the best way to improve a learner's grammar is simply to get them to use the language more. If it is possible to show errors in the use of the language and corrections for these errors then it must be possible to identify the difference between right and wrong.

Finally, there are people who learn a language in a formal setting to use for specific purposes, such as a job requirement.

Couples in bilingual relationships often learn each other's languages to some extent, although it is not unusual for one partner to pick up the other's language in a manner more advanced than the other. This is often due to interference from the first language as well as cultural asymmetries.

There are a few basic ways to learn a language. Firstly, a second language can be learned in a classroom setting where English is spoken as a foreign language (that holds also for speakers of other languages, not just native speakers of English). Another common way to learn a language is by moving to a country where it is spoken, either by enrolling in a school or by trial and error. This would be considered total immersion since it is likely that the person would pick up aspects of the language through cultural exposure as well.

Language learning is a complex and lengthy process that involves many interconnected stages. Bilinguals often do not differentiate between language learning and language acquisition. Gaining the ability to speak and understand a new language is a skill that surely takes time as well as conscious effort.

So, language is an important part of our life. It is a means of communication. Communication is a process of transferring information from one entity to another. At the primary stage, both parties understand the information. If the information is understood clearly, the communication is successful. Now, the success of communication depends upon the way we put our ideas. If the ideas are not presented well, no matter what the medium is, the message won't be delivered. Now, the quality of language used decides the effectiveness of ideas. If the quality is good, ideas presented will be more effective. Nowadays, in this fast-growing world, everyone wants to be ahead of others. That's a universal truth. Now, good quality of language gives a cutting edge over others. So, the importance is clear. Language is a base on which we can build our future. That's why language is given great importance in today's education system. Nowadays, there is a trend to learn a foreign language. People learn it for various purposes, some want to go for higher studies, some for a job, and some for tourism. The purposes may be different, but the underlying fact is that they want better communication. So, the quality of language comes into the picture. A

good say in a language comes from effective learning. Hence, the need for language learning is more important today.

As we know learning a new language is not an easy process. However, our fast developing world needs as many skills as you have and in the following article I would like to explain most common problems that many English learners face, and ways to improve them with simple and fun solutions at the same time. As we heard most people say “If only I could learn English better, I could do so much more.” If you also say “yes” for this question I am sure that this article helps you entirely.

To be a good English speaker is to find the balance between rhythm, cultural understanding, pronunciation and a number of other factors that contribute to fluency. That is why it is so important to take a complete and broad (covering many areas) approach to English speaking. The importance of verbal communication in the English language cannot be ignored. It is a basic skill that takes commitment. But, with **the right guidance and resources**, you will be able to master English speaking in no time.

Firstly, I am going to share my experience about learning a new language. When I began learning English for the first time I found it so easy because I was a little girl and my teacher taught me with ordinary lessons like alphabet, poems, games and so on. Nevertheless, year after year my lessons became more serious and difficult as well as I began to face problems with grammar, pronunciation, vocabulary even so, I get acquainted with serious problems while I was preparing for CEFR exam. The first one is vocabulary. Vocabulary is so crucial when we are learning a language. Any language, of course including English, has thousands and thousands of words. In many cases, even those native speakers of the language do not know all the words of that language, there are just too many to learn. Another problem people face in learning English vocabulary is that they learn new words, but they tend to forget what they have learned quite soon after they just learned them. So what can you do? In order to solve this problem there are games to play and methods to learn to improve your English vocabulary. The best simple method I want to suggest is this; just make a little list and write down an English word on one side and the definition to the other side, so keep reading. Once a week, make a list of twenty or thirty words using the word lists, or choose words from other popular websites.

Learning English is a process. More than a process, it's a journey. **Learning English is a voyage into another culture and another world.**

Those who have taken the journey know that it's not an easy one.

And like all of life's ...

As you are making your list, make sure to write down the definitions if you are unsure of them at the same time. Do your best to study and learn these new words. Keep repeating these new words during the week and try to make sentences for each of them. In order to facilitate your work, break the list down into five or six words a day and on your sixth day of vocabulary learning, try to write all your vocab words for the last week. Take your time and do your best. When you are done, review those words and see what you remember. If you use the method above I guarantee you will improve your English vocabulary and not forget the words you have learned.

One of the biggest complaints I heard about when one is learning a new language, is their inability to communicate successfully. Whether it is an issue with reducing their accent, or not knowing the vocabulary and they struggle with poor speaking skills. Therefore now I am going to explain some ways to improve your English speaking skills. Initially, if you want to be more fluent in English you should talk with natives a lot. Now you can say, “How can I talk with a native speaker if I do not live in English speaking countries?” It is 21st century now and it is the century of technologies. There are many apps like Tandem, ELSA, Cambly and there are plenty of people who would love to just talk with you over the phone or internet to help you learn maybe you can offer to teach them a little of your language in return. That way everybody gains something from the experience. If you are in a country or city where you do not have the opportunity to find a native English speaking friend, chatting on the internet is the best thing. Furthermore, try to learn phrases not words. For instance, it is better to learn the phrase “How are you doing?” than learning all words one by one. It can be easy to remember structure and it reduces hesitations. Moreover, another best option to improve speaking are talking to you and thinking in English. When you start speaking your thoughts in English it helps you a lot because you hear your voice and try to correct your mistakes on your own. On the other hand, paraphrasing is also a good thing while you are listening or watching BBCs or TED talks. This will help you to understand better what you are listening or watching. The next important thing that I recommend, you should surround yourself with English.

I am sure that most people tried to watch a movie in English. It is one of the easiest things to do while studying and learning English. But I'll tell you: it's hearing the words spoken out loud. Therefore, I advise

you to read a book. Well, it doesn't have to be a book, but it needs to be in English. As you are reading the book, read it out loud. Yes, it looks simple, but reading out loud will let you hear your English and at the same time, it helps you gain more confidence in speaking English. It does not have to be for a very long time.

“Writing is a significant skill in language production. Its significance increases when it comes to writing in English language which is extensively used for global mediation of knowledge.” (Mahboob, 2014; Marlina & Giri, 2014; Rahman, 2002).

But you should read out loud for at least five minutes a day. Do not give up on this. I think this is an important method to practice and not enough people practice in this manner. Make sure you are pronouncing your words correctly, and if you have to read slowly, that's OK as well. The point is that you are speaking out loud and practicing speaking English. Since many English learners do not have the opportunity to interact with native English speakers, this is one of the best methods to help improve your English speaking skills. Hyland (2003) believes that performance in language development is subject to improvement in writing skills. A text of an effective ESL writer must be cohesive, logical, clearly structured, interesting and properly organized with a wide range of vocabulary and mastery of conventions in mechanics (Jacobs & L, 1981; Hall, 1988).

If you are lucky enough to know an English speaker that you can meet with, and try to meet them in a comfortable place that you can hear each other speak and just spend about an hour talking about any topic that comes to mind but do not forget that it should be someone you are comfortable with so as you are trying to speak, you will not be shy. You can also plan some topics to talk about so you don't waste your time thinking of things to say, maybe you can write down questions you have or have them ask you questions so you can practice answering them.

Overall, language learning can be a complex and challenging process, but with dedication, practice, and support from teachers and peers, students can overcome these obstacles and become proficient in a new language.

There are plenty of other problems in learning English but I think these are some main reasons. I guarantee that if you know these pitfalls and know how to avoid them, every aspect of your English learning will be improved. And you will be a native English speaker in no time. Good Luck!

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